

A Review of Collaborative Filtering Techniques in Recommender Systems

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Abstract—Collaborative filtering is one of the oldest and most widely used techniques in recommender systems. Instead of relying on item content, it leverages user behavior, such as ratings, clicks, or interaction histories, to predict user preferences. This paper reviews the main categories of collaborative filtering, including memory-based and model-based approaches, and presents the mathematical formulations underlying their prediction mechanisms. Key developments in the literature, such as user-based and item-based similarity models and matrix factorization techniques popularized during the Netflix Prize, are discussed. The paper further analyzes practical challenges including data sparsity, cold start, scalability, and popularity bias. Finally, potential improvements such as hybrid models and neural approaches are examined while highlighting the continued relevance of simpler methods in real-world systems.

Index Terms—Recommender systems, collaborative filtering, matrix factorization, similarity, personalization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommender systems are now a basic part of many web platforms. Online shops, video streaming sites, music apps and even educational platforms use some form of recommendation to show users items that might be interesting for them. Without recommendation, users would sometimes be lost because there are simply too many options.

Collaborative filtering, often written as CF, is one of the first techniques used in these systems and is still very popular. The main idea is quite simple and also intuitive. If two users behaved in a similar way in the past, for example by giving similar ratings to many movies, then it is likely they will also agree again on new movies. Or if two items are liked by many of the same users, then they are probably similar items and can be recommended together.

This makes CF different from content based methods, which need item descriptions such as genre, keywords, or tags. CF only needs information about who interacted with what. This makes it attractive when item metadata is missing or not very detailed. On the other hand, CF also has important challenges. If there are not enough interactions, the method becomes weak.

The purpose of this paper is to provide a focused description of collaborative filtering as a recommender system technique. The paper is written at a fairly basic level, not as a fully formal survey, but it still includes formulas and tries to connect theory with practical issues.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section we go through the main families of collaborative filtering methods. First we talk about memory based methods, which use similarity directly, and then model based methods, which learn some parameters from data.

A. Basic Notation

Usually there is a set of users $U = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ and a set of items $I = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. There is a rating matrix $R \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, where $r_{u,i}$ is the rating that user u gave to item i . Many of these entries are missing because in reality most users rate only a small subset of all items.

We also define I_u as the set of items that user u has rated, and U_i as the set of users that rated item i .

B. User Based Collaborative Filtering

User based collaborative filtering was one of the first CF methods. It was used in systems like GroupLens. The idea is to find users who have similar tastes to the active user and use their ratings to predict unknown ratings.

A common similarity measure is Pearson correlation between users u and v :

$$\text{sim}(u, v) = \frac{\sum_{i \in I_{uv}} (r_{u,i} - \bar{r}_u)(r_{v,i} - \bar{r}_v)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i \in I_{uv}} (r_{u,i} - \bar{r}_u)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i \in I_{uv}} (r_{v,i} - \bar{r}_v)^2}}$$

where $I_{uv} = I_u \cap I_v$ is the set of items both users rated and \bar{r}_u is the average rating of user u .

Once these similarities are computed, the predicted rating of user u on a target item j is:

$$\hat{r}_{u,j} = \bar{r}_u + \frac{\sum_{v \in N_k(u)} \text{sim}(u, v)(r_{v,j} - \bar{r}_v)}{\sum_{v \in N_k(u)} |\text{sim}(u, v)|}$$

where $N_k(u)$ is the set of k nearest neighbours of user u . This formula is easy to understand. We adjust the average rating of user u by taking a weighted average of how similar users rated the same item.

C. Item Based Collaborative Filtering

Item based CF was popularized by Amazon and others. Instead of looking for similar users, we look for similar items. This is often more stable because the set of items changes less frequently than the set of users.

A very common similarity measure for items i and j is cosine similarity:

$$\text{sim}(i, j) = \frac{\sum_{u \in U_{ij}} r_{u,i} r_{u,j}}{\sqrt{\sum_{u \in U_i} r_{u,i}^2} \sqrt{\sum_{u \in U_j} r_{u,j}^2}}$$

Here $U_{ij} = U_i \cap U_j$ is the set of users who rated both items. The predicted rating of user u on item j is:

$$\hat{r}_{u,j} = \frac{\sum_{i \in I_u} \text{sim}(j, i) r_{u,i}}{\sum_{i \in I_u} |\text{sim}(j, i)|}$$

In practice we do not use all items in I_u . We only use the top similar items to keep the computation reasonable.

D. Matrix Factorization

Memory based methods work directly with similarities, but they can be slow and they do not generalize well when the matrix is very sparse. Model based CF methods try to learn latent factors.

Matrix factorization is the most famous model based method. It approximates the rating matrix as:

$$R \approx PQ^T$$

where $P \in R^{m \times k}$ is the user factor matrix and $Q \in R^{n \times k}$ is the item factor matrix. The row p_u represents user u in a k dimensional latent space and q_i represents item i .

The predicted rating is:

$$\hat{r}_{u,i} = p_u^T q_i$$

We learn P and Q by minimizing the regularized squared error over observed ratings:

$$\min_{P, Q} \sum_{(u,i) \in \Omega} (r_{u,i} - p_u^T q_i)^2 + \lambda (\|p_u\|^2 + \|q_i\|^2)$$

where Ω is the set of known ratings and λ is a regularization parameter.

A more complete version includes a global mean and biases:

$$\hat{r}_{u,i} = \mu + b_u + b_i + p_u^T q_i$$

where μ is the global average rating, b_u is user bias, and b_i is item bias.

Matrix factorization models gave very strong results in the Netflix Prize and are still widely used.

E. Evaluation Metrics in Literature

Most papers evaluate CF models using metrics such as mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE):

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{|\Omega_{\text{test}}|} \sum_{(u,i) \in \Omega_{\text{test}}} |r_{u,i} - \hat{r}_{u,i}|$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|\Omega_{\text{test}}|} \sum_{(u,i) \in \Omega_{\text{test}}} (r_{u,i} - \hat{r}_{u,i})^2}$$

For top k recommendation tasks, ranking metrics like Precision at k , Recall at k and normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG) are also used.

III. OBSERVATION AND ANALYSIS

After reading several works and also looking at the formulas, some points become quite clear.

First, collaborative filtering can provide very good personalization when there is enough data. If the system has many users and many ratings, then similar users and items can be identified quite reliably. Matrix factorization is especially strong because it can capture hidden factors, like a user preference for dark humour in movies, without needing that label explicitly.

Second, memory based methods like user based CF are simple and easy to implement, but they do not scale very well. Computing similarity between all pairs of users is expensive. Item based CF is better for large catalogs because the number of items is smaller and stable compared to the number of users, but still, similarity matrices can be large.

Third, data sparsity is a major problem. In real systems like movie recommenders or shopping platforms, each user only interacts with a tiny fraction of all items. The rating matrix R is mostly empty. This makes similarity scores noisy and sometimes meaningless, especially if two users have only one or two items in common.

Fourth, cold start situations are difficult. When a new user joins, the system has almost no data about them, so CF cannot compute similarity. The same is true for new items with no ratings. In those cases, CF is basically blind.

Fifth, there is a strong popularity bias effect. Items that are already popular get more interactions, which then makes them more likely to be recommended again. This feedback loop makes it harder for less known items to be discovered. In some domains this is not a big issue, but in others it can be unfair.

Another observation is about interpretability. User based and item based methods are somewhat interpretable. You can say, this movie is recommended because many users similar to you liked it. But matrix factorization is harder to explain because the latent factors do not always have a clear meaning. Neural network based CF is even more like a black box.

Finally, from a classification or regression point of view, CF models can overfit if regularization is not used properly. This is especially visible in smaller datasets where the model can memorize noise instead of learning real patterns.

IV. SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

There are several ways to improve collaborative filtering methods and many of them are discussed in existing research.

One common solution is to build hybrid systems that combine CF with content based methods. Item features such as genres, tags, descriptions or even images can be used along with CF. For example, when a new item appears, a content based model can still recommend it even if there are no

ratings yet. Over time, CF can then take over when enough interactions have been collected.

Another improvement is to use trust or social relationships. If the platform has information about which users know or follow each other, then these links can be used to adjust similarity. Ratings from trusted friends can be given more weight. This can be useful especially when data is sparse.

Matrix factorization itself can be improved in many directions. For implicit feedback data, where there are no explicit ratings but only clicks or views, weighted regularized matrix factorization and factorization machines have been proposed. These models treat missing entries differently and try to handle confidence in the interactions.

Neural collaborative filtering and autoencoder based systems can model non linear interactions between users and items. These models can, in theory, fit more complex patterns, but they also need careful tuning and are not always easy to train. Graph based methods using graph neural networks extend CF to user item graphs and can use multiple hops of neighbours, but again with higher complexity.

Another group of improvements focuses on fairness, diversity and novelty. Instead of only optimizing for accuracy, the recommendation list can be modified to include less popular items or to increase variety. There is a trade off here between showing the safest choice and exploring new items for the user.

Finally, privacy is becoming a major concern. Traditional CF requires the system to collect and store user ratings or interaction logs. Privacy preserving methods such as federated learning and differential privacy techniques aim to train CF models without exposing raw user data. For example, user factor updates can be computed locally on the user device and only aggregated by the server.

V. LIMITATIONS

This work is a conceptual and literature-based review and does not include new experimental evaluation or empirical benchmarking. Future work may extend this study with comparative experiments on benchmark datasets to provide quantitative insights into the discussed techniques.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper we looked at collaborative filtering as a recommender system technique in some detail. We started from the basic user based and item based similarity models, then moved to matrix factorization and more modern neural approaches. We also discussed common evaluation metrics and pointed out typical problems like sparsity, cold start and popularity bias.

Collaborative filtering is not a perfect method, but it has several strong advantages. It does not need item content information, it learns directly from real user behavior, and it can capture subtle patterns through latent factors. Because of these strengths, CF is still a central method in many production recommender systems.

At the same time, CF should not be used blindly. In practice, it is often combined with other techniques to form hybrid systems, and many engineering tricks are needed to deal with scale, privacy and fairness. From this review it seems clear that collaborative filtering will remain important, but in combination with other modern methods rather than alone.

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